

Analysis of Intensity-Duration-Frequency and Depth-Duration-Frequency Curve Projections under Climate Variability

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This study focuses on the design of Intensity duration frequency (IDF) curves for the Raipur city in Chhattisgarh state, Central India under climate variability. The originality of this study comes with the attention of temporal rainfall variability consideration in design rainfall. To track the inherent rainfall event, shorter duration rainfall data has been used. As the shorter duration rainfall data will give the precise number of rainfall event which may be ignored in higher duration rainfall event. The insight of the result gives the asses to check the vulnerability of the hydraulic structure as well as planning, designing and operation under climate uncertainty. The Gumbels extreme value distribution was used to find the design intensity for different duration and different intensity at different return period. The annual maximum series of precipitation intensity for each duration is obtained and K-S & Chi-Square tests were performed to check the fitness of the rainfall data. To consider the non-stationarity of the rainfall, time series is divided into two parts from the change point. Trend of each series represents the change in intensity of the rainfall with time. These results are explaining the importance of the adaptation of changed climate.

Keywords: Climate shift, Climate variability, Intensity-Duration-Frequency Curve, Trend analysis, Raipur city